

IS BENEFICIAL TRANSLATING REALIA

Sharifa Hamroyeva Shukurovna

Teacher Of Bukhara State University, Uzbekistan

Shohnigor Jurayeva

Student of Bukhara State University, Uzbekistan

Annotation: In this article it was comprised Realia and it is difficulties during the translation. There are some type of Realia introduced which requires solution in this time and a number of solutions that can be necessary for exact issues.

Keywords: realia , culture-oriented , conative lexicon, background lexicon, Cultural-educational , Material-household

Introduction:

In our modern age, where great attention is paid to the theory of linguistics, the potential of the English language and translation is highly valued. Translation activities, especially for the purpose of a deeper study of the culture and race of a certain country, create a foundation for the development of the young generation in all aspects, because every nation has its own culture. That is why translation is one of the most difficult parts of the field of science, it not only clearly shows the history and ethnic characteristics of peoples and nations, but also helps to gain deep knowledge about their characteristics and cultures.

At the moment, there are such types as realia and culture-oriented words in the translation activity, which also consist of different components like :

Realia

Conative lexicon

Background lexicon

A term of Realia is commonly used during Roman emperors and middle ages in Europe, however, this word firstly founded by Latins so it is in latin means “ real things or actual facts, especially as distinct from theories about or reactions to them” as well different styles of languages . Linguistic differences notwithstanding, it should be careful not to confuse the field of

Realia with the field of terms.

May be divided into the geographic and ethnographic realia. The geographic realias are names of the geographic and atmospheric objects and endemic species.

Translation of the realia demands the translator to be especially careful. Although that can be clear that :

The notions and objects which may be accurately described and defined, while translating them into the target language there may occur remarkable deviations and variations. It is connected with the fact that by the frequency of use, by the role in the language, by the household meaning, the words naming the realias do not have any term colouring; they do not outstand even in the most everyday content of the source text thus being usual for the source language which is the biggest difficulty for the translator. There are some issue has been researched intensively and skillfully enough, but from our point of view it still remains relevant and, in some way, quite new for the modern scientists, because life of people is developing and changing thus creating new realia, notions which need to be studied. Also this issue is still relevant, because we may find fields of the realia research which have not been studied well and try to observe the realia in these unknown fields. To enter this field it is necessary to understand what «realia» is in the first place, both

Within translation studies and without scientific sectors.

Main part:

Types. Translated foreign idioms has diverse groups with it's features as according to Newmark it just divided into six : material culture, natural culture, social culture, educational culture, ecological culture and folklore as its using methods during exact occasions. But they all should be included in two main sides like:

Cultural-educational and Material-household

And they both also include : material culture, social culture and custom actions into cultural -educational Realia ; Ecology, natural features, historical itematic idioms into material-household ones , because they all six type depending on each other by this two main groups . In addition Russian scientist said according to its regional and ethical division it collected into ten groups at all , then they geography , household, folklore... etc. In some views they all can be united into this two points which had shown above .

Difficulties:

It is clear that to communicate the definition of the objects used in the source language and the images connected with them, it is necessary to have definite awareness of the reality described in the source text. In the theory of translation such awareness is called «background» which is a complex of the ideas about the real background of the life in the country of the source language. Background lexicon is

the words or expressions bearing some additional meaning and definite semantics so there are some difficulties during translation.

A lot of Ukrainian, Russian and foreign researchers devoted their work to the study of the Realia. This issue has been researched intensively and skillfully enough, but from our point of view it still remains relevant and, in some way, quite new for the modern scientists, because life of people is developing and changing thus creating new realia, notions which need to be studied. Also this issue is still relevant, because we may find the fields of the realia research which have not been studied well and try to observe the realia in these unknown fields.

On the other side, In the process of translation, its text must be translated according to the type of its division, otherwise it will be incomprehensible to the reader. And sometimes we can not find real equivalent to word which are related to deep cultural points. Since the idioms and words in realia are related to the culture and history of another country, it is necessary to fully study the history and cultural life of that country first, which requires a lot of time and effort from the translator.

For example Tsundoku (Japanese) So, you've purchased all those classics you said you'd read – but then they end up piling up on the floor, gathering dust. This word describes hoarding books and never reading them.

Shemomedjamo (Georgian) This word describes someone knowing he or she is full, but continuing to eat anyway.

Scottish word "tartle," refers to a situation in which a person can't introduce someone because they've forgotten their name.

Solutions:

First of all after facing with Realia we should to deeply understand the words which are not translated to English and try to find some ways that can be easily mean able by readers. Time is changing at dramatically stages for reason why we also create a knowledge about todays life cause linguistic fields are growing as the same pages, appearing some new word that can be fully different from historical ones: "google" is a perfect example of such a term. It came into use in the early 2000s after the Google search engine became popular. People needed a verb that would mean searching for information in Google, so Americans made a verb out of the engine's name. Other languages have never felt like they needed to develop a translation for this verb, so they borrowed it as it was and kept it to use.

Government should create some subjects about Realia on the field of linguistic skills so all students can be aware from some interesting words from a lot of cultures.

Indeed, it can help to improve the horizons of generation and brings the feelings of awareness among all countries.

Conclusion

Translating words that cannot be translated in English has its benefit for present life unless having some troubles. During translation scientist should know not only some aspects of knowledge about certain countries but also about tradition and time of Realia that is being reusable into duration of some periods.

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